

THE EFFECT OF AUDIO BANDWIDTH ON SELECTED DIGITAL SPEECH CODING ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

The speech intelligibility in noise of three different digital speech coding algorithms was investigated at the standard audio bandwidth of 300 to 3400 Hz and a developmental bandwidth of 100-6000 Hz. Speech intelligibility was measured using a standardized instrument, the Modified Rhyme Test (MRT). Performance was investigated at three different levels of an acoustic noise environment. This report presents results, discussion, conclusions and recommendations for further research.

INTRODUCTION

Voice communications play a vital role in military operations. With the arrival of sophisticated electronic counter measures (ECM), the voice communication system designer has been moving toward digital communication links in which jam resistance and security can be more easily incorporated. Speech coding algorithms are used to change the analog voice signal into a stream of "1's" and "0's" to be transmitted over these digital communication links and reconstructed into an analog voice signal at the receiver. A large number of these systems are expected to operate in aircraft or other vehicles where high ambient noise environments are present.

The articulation index calculation developed by Kryter (ref 1) is the design tool of choice to determine the optimum bandwidth for a voice communication system. Applying this articulation index calculation to pink noise (a reasonable representation of jet cockpit noise spectra, i.e. equal energy per octave) most designers arrive at the 3300 to 3500 Hz upper bandwidth limit for best communication capability. Any additional bandwidth provides more noise power than voice power and therefore lowers the overall signal to noise ratio which lowers the intelligibility. However, the articulation index was developed for analog voice communication systems, most of which are fairly linear. With the advent of digital voice communication systems and their non-linear coding algorithms, the possibility exists that

the articulation index may not be an accurate predictor of intelligibility.

BACKGROUND

Researchers at the Armstrong Aerospace Medical Research Laboratory, Biological Acoustics Branch (AAMRL/BBA), during the past five years, have investigated the performance in acoustic noise of various voice communication systems utilizing digital speech coding algorithms. These efforts include the investigation of two algorithms for a spread spectrum communication system (1) continuously variable slope delta (CVSD) and (2) pulse width modulation (PWN) (ref 2); five algorithms for the Worldwide Airborne Military Command System communication links (1) linear predictive coding (LPC), (2) sub-band coding (SBC), (3) sub-band coding with time domain harmonic scaling (SBC-TDHS), (4) CVSD and (5) adaptive differential pulse code modulation (ADPCM) (ref 3); and two algorithm types for the tri-service standard Digital Audio Distribution System (DADS), (1) pulse code modulation (PCM) and (2) ADPCM. In these experiments, indications were found that increased bandwidth might improve intelligibility in high level acoustic noise environs. The decision was made to investigate this possibility under controlled laboratory conditions.

OBJECTIVE

The objective was to determine what effect, if any, increased audio bandwidth had on the intelligibility of digital speech coding algorithms operating in high acoustic noise environs.

APPROACH

Speech intelligibility measurements were made on three basic coding algorithms, two waveform coders, (PCM at 56 kilo bits per second (kbps) and ADPCM at 16 kbps and 32 kbps) and three different versions of a parametric coder, (the government standard LPC algorithm, a MIT Lincoln Labs standard LPC algorithm and a MIT Lincoln Labs enhanced LPC algorithm designed to take advantage of increased audio bandwidth). The two

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bandwidths selected were 300-3400 Hz as in the Air Force standard intercommunication system and the 100-6000 Hz bandwidth selected for use in DADS. The audio communication bandwidths were adjusted for the LPC algorithms by variable analog bandpass filters. The PCM & ADPCM bandwidth was adjusted by changing the sampling rate on the A/D - D/A convertor. The experiments were conducted in pink noise environments of 75, 85 and 95 dB re 20µPa overall sound pressure level (OASPL). These noise levels simulated to a certain extent the signal to noise ratios (SNR) for listeners wearing standard military communications headsets operating in 95, 105 and 115 dB OASPL noise environments. The military headsets provide approximately 15 dB more high frequency acoustic noise attenuation than was modelled by this study, therefore the data presented underestimates the communication performance that would be seen in actual applications, especially at the higher noise levels. However, this method gives a good indication of the relative performance of the digital speech coding algorithms at the different bandwidth and noise level conditions of the study.

FACILITIES

A. Equipment - This experiment was conducted in the AAMRL/BBA Voice Communication Research and Evaluation System. This system duplicates the entire voice communication link between the talker and listener (Figure 1), allowing the capability to realistically emulate the major factors that may adversely affect voice communications. The experimental communication system includes a master-control station and 10 individual communication stations. Each station contains a standard AIC/25 intercommunication system, wideband intercommunication system and respiration system (A-19 Oxygen Regulators), as well as appropriate terminal equipment, i.e., headsets, helmets, oxygen masks and microphones. Each station is integrated with a Computer Display-Response system in which the central processor is a Hewlett-Packard 9845T. An interface at each station decodes commands by the central processor for the station's display and also returns the subject's response to the

Figure 1.

central processor for storage and analysis. The acoustic environment simulation facility consists of a reverberation chamber (approximately 3,000 cubic ft) that houses an electrodynamic sound system. The electrodynamic system contains five 600 watt audio amplifiers. The amplifiers drive a four-way loudspeaker system containing four 15-inch loudspeakers, four 12-inch loudspeakers, twelve high frequency compression drivers with horns, and twelve ultra high-frequency compression drivers with horns. In the configuration used for this experiment, the system is capable of a maximum of 130 dB, with a pink noise input.

B. Subjects - Ten volunteer subjects, five male and five female, were employed in the experiment. All were recruited from the general civilian population. They were paid at an hourly rate for their participation, with a cash bonus awarded when all sessions were completed. The hearing levels of all subjects were no greater than 15 dB at any standard audiometric test frequency from 500 to 6000 Hz. All talkers wore the standard Air Force Flight Helmet (HGU-26/P), with the H-154A Earcup Assembly. Helmets were individually fitted to each subject. The MBU-12/P AF Oxygen Mask with the M-101 Noise Cancelling Microphone was worn by each talker. All listeners wore Yamaha UH-1 high fidelity headphones. The talkers respired compressed air through A-19 Diluter Demand Pressure Breathing Regulators set at normal operation. All subjects were trained for at least 4 hours on each different coding algorithm before data collection.

C. Measurement Instrument - Speech intelligibility was quantified using a standardized measure of intelligibility, the Modified Rhyme Test (MRT). The MRT was developed by House, et al. (Ref 5) to assess communication effectiveness. The materials consist of lists of 50 one-syllable words that are equivalent (lists) in intelligibility. These test words are presented embedded within a carrier phrase that is the same for each item. The MRT is easy to administer, score and evaluate, and it does not require extensive training of listeners. MRT word intelligibility has been sufficiently standardized to allow the relative intelligibility of such materials as closed-message sets and sentences to be estimated on the basis of measured MRT scores (Ref 6). To compensate for correct answers obtained by guessing, a correction factor was applied to the scores during data analysis. This correction for guessing ($\# \text{ correct} - \# \text{ wrong} / \# \text{ possible choices} - 1$) was subtracted from the total number correct for each subject.

RESULTS

The effect of bandwidth on speech intelligibility in the noise environments

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investigated is shown in Figures 2-8. PCM (Figure 2) shows a nearly constant 5% advantage for the 6000 Hz bandwidth over the 3400 Hz bandwidth across the three acoustic noise levels. In Figure 3, ADPCM at 16 kbps shows a 12% to 15% intelligibility advantage of the 6000 kHz bandwidth at the medium and high noise levels. Figure 4, ADPCM at 32 kbps, shows a even more dramatic advantage for the 6000 kHz bandwidth at the 95 dB level (23%), while the 6000 Hz advantage at 75 and 85 dB is comparable to that for 16 KPBS (3% and 10% respectively). Figure 5, shows an average of 16, 24, 32, and 40 kbps ADPCM at the 3400 Hz and 6000 Hz bandwidths. As can be seen, the 6000 Hz advantage increases with increasing noise levels. Figure 6 depicts the government standard 2.4 kbps LPC performance. The government standard algorithm is the only condition in this experiment where the 3400 Hz bandwidth has an advantage over the 6000 Hz bandwidth, however, the advantage is small. Figure 7, the MIT standard 2.4 kbps LPC algorithm, once again shows an advantage for the 6000 Hz bandwidth (approximately 10%). Figure 8 (MIT enhanced 2.4 kbps LPC) shows the best performance for any of the three 2.4 kbps LPC versions at the 6000 Hz bandwidth.

16 KBPS ADPCM

Figure 3.

PCM

Figure 2.

32 KBPS ADPCM

Figure 4.

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AVERAGE OF ADPCM

Figure 5.

MIT STANDARD LPC

Figure 7.

GOV'T STANDARD LPC

Figure 6.

MIT ENHANCED LPC

Figure 8.

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DISCUSSION

The reasons for the advantage of the 6000 Hz bandwidth at this point are only conjecture. Even though the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) may deteriorate with increasing bandwidth in the 3400 to 6000 Hz region, the ability to extract speech from noise under poor SNR conditions is well documented (ref 7). The intelligibility may increase with wider bandwidth because of the additional information available to the listener. Also, the AI calculation may not be appropriate for digital systems, especially non-linear systems, and a new method of predicting speech intelligibility in noise may need to be researched and developed. The government standard 2.4 kbps LPC algorithm, where the 3400 Hz bandwidth was superior, was designed especially for the 3400 Hz audio bandwidth.

CONCLUSIONS

Intelligibility of three different types of digital speech coders in noise was measured over two audio bandwidths, 300-3400 Hz and 100-6000 Hz. In all but one case the 100-6000 Hz bandwidth resulted in superior performance. The advantage in several cases was greater at higher acoustic noise levels. This performance is opposite to that expected using predictive measures such as the articulation index. Possibly a new method needs to be developed to predict intelligibility of digital speech communication systems.

REFERENCES

1. Kryter, K. D., "Methods for the Calculation and use of the Articulation Index," J. Acoust. Soc. Amer., Vol. 34, 1962, pp. 1689-1697.
2. Moore, T. J., McKinley, R. L., Mortimer, V. D., Nixon, C. W., "Evaluation of Word Intelligibility of Two Modems of a Spread Spectrum Communication System in Presence of Simulated Cockpit Noise," AMRL-TR-78-54.
3. McKinley, R. L., Kurtz, R. V., "Subjective Performance of Selected Speech Coders in the Presence of Channel Errors." Proceedings 1984 IEEE Military Communications Conference, Vol. 3, 1984, pp. 521-526.
4. McKinley, R. L., "Voice Communication Research and Evaluation," AMRL-TR-80-25, 1980.
5. House, A. S., Williams, C. W., Hecker, M. H. L., Kryter, K. D., "Articulation Testing Methods: Consonantal Differentiation with a Closed Response Set," J. Acoust. Soc. Amer., 37, 1965, 158-166.
6. Webster, J. C., "Compendium of Speech Testing Material and Typical Noise Spectra for use in Evaluation Communications Equipment." NECC Tech Document 191, Sep 1972.

7. Suter, Alice H., "The Ability of Mildly Hearing-Impaired Individuals to Discriminate Speech in Noise," EPA 550/9-78-100, AMRL-TR-78-4, Jan 78.